

Simposio
ESTRATEGIAS INMUNOLÓGICAS, FARMACOLÓGICAS,
ANTIPARASITARIAS Y ANTITUMORALES EN TORNO
A *TRYPANOSOMA CRUZI*

Tissue responses again parasites and tumor invasion: differences and similarities in extracellular matrix reorganization

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The extracellular matrix is a key regulator of cell and tissue function. Traditionally, the extracellular matrix is considered as a physical scaffold that binds cells and tissues together (5). However, the extracellular matrix is a dynamic structure that interacts with cells and generates signals through feedback loops to control the behavior of cells. Thus, extracellular matrix macromolecules are bioactive and modulate cellular events such as adhesion, migration, proliferation, differentiation, and survival (3). Additionally, extracellular matrix molecules are strictly organized and this organization determines the bioactivity of it. Even minor alterations in a single extracellular matrix component can lead not only to altered physicochemical properties of tissues but also to changes in cellular phenotype and cell-matrix interactions. It has been proposed that these changes in extracellular matrix structure and bioactivity in tissue function ultimately lead to development of disease (6).

Parasites and neoplastic cells, during tissue invasion or tumor dissemination, modify extracellular matrix in order to modulate host immune responses and facilitate the mobilization inside the tissues (2,4). *Trypanosoma cruzi*, the causative agent of Chagas disease, induces changes in extracellular matrix in different tissues, for example in myocardium (7) and in human placental chorionic villi (4). Neoplastic cells modify host microenvironment that undergoes extensive changes during the evolution and progression of cancer. This involves the generation of cancer-associated fibroblasts, which, through release of growth factors and cytokines, lead to

enhanced angiogenesis, increased tumor growth and invasion. The altered fibroblast phenotype also contributes to the development of an altered extracellular matrix. The inflammatory infiltrate associated with many solid tumors also modulates tumor function, having both anti- and pro-tumor effects (1).

We have analyzed changes in extracellular matrix induced by *T. cruzi* in human placental chorionic villi as well as those induced in tumor stroma and neighboring connective tissue by oral squamous cell carcinoma and by salivary papillary cystadenocarcinoma.

Extracellular matrix changes induced by *Trypanosoma cruzi* in human placental chorionic villi

The human placenta is classified as a hemochorial villous placenta in which the free chorionic villi are the functional units. These chorionic villi are formed by the trophoblast and the villous stroma. The trophoblast is formed by a single multinucleated cell layer (syncytiotrophoblast) which contacts maternal blood in the intervillous space, and by the cytotrophoblast which contains replicating progenitor cells. The trophoblast is separated by a basal lamina from the villous stroma, which is connective tissue containing vascular endothelium, fibroblasts, and macrophages. Trophoblast, basal laminae, and villous stroma with endothelium of fetal capillaries form the placental barrier that must be crossed by different pathogens, including *T. cruzi*, in order to infect the fetus during vertical transmission (4).

Trypanosoma cruzi induces syncytiotrophoblast destruction and detachment, selective disorganization of basal lamina and disorganization of collagen I in the connective tissue of villous stroma. These effects can be observed in placentas of mothers with chronic asymptomatic Chagas disease as well as in *ex vivo* infected chorionic villi explants. In the chorionic villi explants these effects are a function of the number of parasites used for the infection. The destruction of the extracellular matrix is product of activation of proteases of the parasite (cruzipain) and matrix metalloproteases (MMP) of the placental tissue. *Trypanosoma cruzi* induces expression and activity of MMP-2 and MMP-9 in chorionic villi explants. Inhibition of the proteases prevents partially the extracellular matrix destruction induced by the parasite.

It has been proposed that extracellular matrix alterations produced by *T. cruzi* not only promote its motility in tissues and its entrance into cells, but also alter the presence of cytokines and chemokines, which in turn permit this parasite to modulate and escape both the inflammatory response and the immune response (4,7). Alternatively, these changes in extracellular matrix function may be part of local placental defense mechanisms, which could explain both the low presence of parasites in the placenta and the low incidence of congenital Chagas disease.

Extracellular matrix changes in neoplastic lesions with different degree of malignancy

Cancer cell migration and invasion into adjacent connective tissue depends on extracellular matrix, which provides a physical scaffold for cell adhesion and migration. Proteolysis of the extracellular matrix regulates cellular migration by modifying the structure of the extracellular matrix scaffold and by releasing extracellular matrix fragments with biological functions. Extracellular matrix proteolysis is therefore tightly controlled in normal tissues but typically deregulated in tumors (5). Changes in extracellular matrix in areas of invasive tumor front are used in some systems to classify neoplastic lesion of epithelia origin, like the Bryne's multifactorial grading system for the invasive tumor front (8).

In highly invasive (poor differentiated) oral squamous cell carcinoma destruction of basal

lamina and disorganization of collagen I in adjacent connective tissue is present. Contrarily, in low grade papillary cystadenocarcinoma and well differentiated oral squamous cell carcinoma only in some focal areas a slight discontinuity can be observed and the collagen I in the adjacent connective tissue is well organized.

Therefore the organization of the extracellular matrix can prevent or facilitate the tumor invasion and dissemination. Poor differentiated tumors modify the extracellular matrix in order to facilitate the invasion process. Contrarily, well differentiated tumors are not able to modify the extracellular matrix and the tissue can impair the invasion and dissemination of the neoplastic lesion.

In summary, parasite and tumors induces extracellular matrix responses that can facilitate or impair tissue invasion. The extracellular matrix response depends on the type of aggression (parasite, type of tumor) as well as of the type of tissue that is being challenged.

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and produces reactive species through the Fenton reaction affecting epimastigotes. On the other hand, trypomastigotes are under the attack of ROS/NOS in the parasitophore vesicle while amastigotes suffer the effect of the reactive species inside mammalian cells. To establish a chronic infection some parasites must resist the oxidative damage. Although all cellular macromolecules are subject to damage, the primary deleterious consequences of oxidative stress probably arise from damage to DNA. However, to date we are not aware about reports showing oxidative damage in *T. cruzi* DNA. Additionally, the capacity as well as the mechanisms responsible for the repair of the DNA damage is also unknown. We propose that the parasite DNA is damaged but it is repaired via the base excision repair pathway that is activated when *T. cruzi* is exposed to ROS/RNS, allowing its survival.

We report that H_2O_2 and NOO^\cdot induce oxidative nuclear and kineplastid DNA damage in *T. cruzi* that may be partially repaired by the parasite. Furthermore, we show that both oxidative agents diminish cell viability of *T. cruzi* epimastigotes and trypomastigotes. This effect is significantly augmented in parasites subsequently incubated with the drug methoxyamine, an inhibitor of the apurinic/apyrimidinic enzymes involved in the base excision repair pathway of DNA repair, suggesting that the base excision repair pathway is indeed activated after oxidative damage to the parasite. The diminution of cell viability after ROS/NOS attack is most probably due to a population of parasites unable to repair their DNA. On the contrary, the maintenance of *T. cruzi* viability is a consequence of DNA repair mechanisms, most probably sustained by the base excision repair pathway.

We have cloned, expressed and identified by mass spectrometry three recombinant *T. cruzi* DNA repair enzymes (TcAP1, TcAP2 and NL1Tc). As analyzed by modelling, these enzymes present structural characteristics similar but not equal to mammalian ones. Using an antibody prepared against TcAP1 peptides we recognized presence of this enzyme in the three cellular forms of the parasite. Transfected TcAP1-GFP and TcAP2-GFP to epimastigotes show that TcAP1 and TcAP2 are localized in the nucleus but not in the kinetoplast of the parasite. Overexpression of both enzymes independently, increases survival of parasites when submitted to oxidative stress.

Our results show that *T. cruzi* DNA is damaged when exposed to H_2O_2 and NOO^\cdot and that this damage is partially repaired by the parasite. Inhibition of the base excision repair pathway by methoxyamine diminishes parasite viability when exposed to oxidative agents. At least two *T. cruzi* enzymes of the base excision repair pathway were cloned and expressed. It is proposed that inhibition of DNA repair represents a possible therapeutic target for the control of *T. cruzi* infection, particularly if this target is articulated with the conventional drugs used for Chagas disease treatment.

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